

Soundsketcher: A Visual Interface for Perceptual Exploration of Electroacoustic Sound

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Abstract

This paper presents Soundsketcher, a system for the perceptually grounded visualisation of electroacoustic music. Selected spectral, pitch-related, timbral, and psychoacoustic features, individually and in combination, are mapped onto visual dimensions informed by research on crossmodal correspondences. The system operates on separated audio streams using frame-based analysis and supports alternative rendering strategies, including line-based and polygon-based sketching. A controlled synthetic example is used to examine the behaviour of alternative feature-to-visual mapping strategies, particularly in relation to the representation of tonal and noise-dominated material. In addition, a short excerpt from Pierre Schaeffer's *Étude aux objets* serves as a musical illustration of the framework when applied to musical material. The paper discusses practical limitations of frame-based analysis and considers the role of mapping design in shaping visual interpretation. Soundsketcher is presented as a flexible framework for exploring how perceptually salient features of electroacoustic sound may be computationally articulated and visually externalised.

1. Introduction

This paper presents Soundsketcher, a system for the visualisation of electroacoustic sound based on perceptual principles. A first version of the system was introduced at the Sound and Music Computing Conference (SMC 2025) by Velenis et al. (2025). The present paper expands that work by clarifying the theoretical assumptions that guide its design. The starting point of the project is a simple question: how can organised sound be rendered visually? More specifically, how can sound that unfolds through spectral transformation, density variation, and morphological evolution be articulated visually without reducing it to symbolic abstractions?

Although numerous tools exist for spectral analysis, such as IRCAM's *Partiels* (IRCAM n.d.) and *Sonic Visualiser* (Cannam et al. 2006), as well as visual annotation environments like *Acousmographie* (Battier and Couprie 1999) and *iAnalyse* (Couprie 2019), these systems serve different purposes. Analytical environments primarily provide detailed measurements and inspection of acoustic parameters, without aiming to articulate perceptual organisation through visual form. Conversely, visual annotation tools support the representation of morphological structures, yet typically rely on manual input rather than automated feature extraction.

This paper addresses this gap by proposing a perceptually grounded approach to visualisation and describing its computational realisation. Soundsketcher is treated here not simply as a software tool, but as a case study through which questions of perceptual and morphological organisation (Smalley 1997; Schaeffer 1966), crossmodal mapping (Spence and Di Stefano 2024; Adeli et al. 2014), and visual articulation can be explored. The paper is structured in three parts: theoretical framing, perceptually grounded visual design, and computational implementation demonstrated through a case study.

2. Background and Theoretical Context

The development of electroacoustic music in the mid-twentieth century challenged representational systems centered on pitch and metric organisation. Works structured through evolving spectra, dynamic mass, and textural transformation exceed the descriptive scope of conventional pitch- and meter-based notation. This has led not only to alternative graphic practices, but also to systematic attempts at symbolic representation within acousmatic analysis (e.g., Thoresen and Hedman 2007, 2015; Sköld 2022). This shift prompted the emergence of alternative descriptive frameworks capable of addressing sound as process rather than as succession of note events.

Composers and analysts therefore explored new strategies of visual representation. Graphic notation traditions expanded the visual language of composition beyond staff notation, often functioning as prescriptive systems intended to guide performance. In contrast, *aural scores* for electroacoustic works are produced retrospectively, after the sound material exists. Rather than instructing performance, they translate perceptually salient structures within recorded sound into visual form, reflecting an analytic listening process rather than a compositional prescription (Schröder 2010).

This analytic orientation toward the perceptual organisation of sound is closely related to Pierre Schaeffer's concept of the *objet sonore* (Schaeffer 1966). Through *reduced listening*, attention is directed toward intrinsic sonic traits like mass, grain, duration, or spectral behavior, while source and semantic reference are set aside. The sound object is defined not by what produces it, but by how it is perceived as a coherent unit. Later theorists reformulated this distinction in different contexts. Chion, for example, differentiates between causal, semantic, and reduced listening (Chion 1994), while Landy proposes contextual, heightened, passive, and musical listening (Landy EARS2). These listening typologies suggest that any visualisation of sound implicitly aligns with a particular mode of attention.

In *spectromorphology*, Smalley (1997) describes sound in terms of spectral movement, density, and temporal shaping, emphasizing transformation as a primary structural principle. From this perspective, form is apprehended as a process: a gradual development of mass, texture, and energy over time. In such cases, representations based exclusively on discrete units may not fully capture the perceptual continuity of sound processes.

Soundsketcher aligns primarily with a reduced listening stance. Its mappings are not designed to visualise source identity or semantic reference, but to trace perceptual configurations emerging from the perceptible properties of the sound itself. Any visualisation of sound therefore presupposes a listening position. If listening is perceptually organised, visual

representation must account for this organisation. The question then becomes how auditory traits can be articulated visually.

Research on crossmodal correspondences suggests that listeners tend to associate certain auditory and visual dimensions in systematic ways, for example: pitch with vertical elevation, loudness with size, timbral sharpness with angularity, and brightness with luminance (Spence and Di Stefano 2024; Adeli et al. 2014; Giannos et al. 2024). These associations have been observed repeatedly across experimental studies, indicating that they are not purely arbitrary conventions. At the same time, crossmodal correspondences do not prescribe a single or absolute mapping between sound and image. They describe tendencies rather than rules, allowing for variation depending on context, experience, and task. They therefore offer not a definitive visual translation of sound, but a direction toward perceptually shared intuitions.

Within this theoretical context, Soundsketcher is positioned as a computational visual framework for generating perceptually grounded representations of recorded sound, in dialogue with the tradition of aural scores. Rather than encoding performance gestures or symbolic abstractions, the system maps spectral and temporal features onto visual dimensions informed by research on crossmodal correspondences. These mappings reflect recurrent associations observed between sound and image, offering plausible, though not prescriptive, relations across modalities. While default configurations follow these tendencies, they remain adjustable, acknowledging the contextual and interpretive nature of perceptual organisation.

3. From Perceptual Theory to Visual Representation

Before outlining the system, it is useful to clarify the conceptual assumptions that guide it. The approach does not begin from predefined musical units. Instead, it traces the evolution of selected spectral and temporal features across time. In many electroacoustic contexts, sound unfolds through gradual transformation rather than clearly bounded events. The visual framework therefore focuses on evolving configurations of features rather than symbolic structures.

Continuity is constructed through progressive variation of parameters such as spectral centroid, roughness, loudness, and periodicity, among others. What is rendered visually is a changing configuration of these features. Coherence emerges when relations among them remain relatively stable over a temporal span; boundaries appear only when those relations shift significantly. In the computational implementation, these dimensions are selectively mapped onto visual parameters, allowing perceptual relations to be traced graphically. The approach is intentionally selective. It does not attempt to reproduce the full acoustic signal, but to foreground dimensions that contribute to perceptual organisation. The result stands between spectrogram and score: it neither displays raw measurement nor encodes symbolic notation, but traces evolving relations among selected auditory parameters.

In computational terms, this framework relies on frame-based analysis. Short temporal segments allow the tracking of feature variation. However, perceptual organisation does not operate as a sequence of discrete frames. Listeners integrate information across time, forming coherent streams and objects (Bregman 1990). Frames therefore function as analytical tools; visual continuity emerges through relations established across them.

Soundsketcher implements this framework through a stream-based analysis of separated audio signals. A detailed description of the system architecture and implementation is provided in (Velenis et al. 2025); the focus here is on the alignment between conceptual assumptions and computational design choices.

The system analyses each audio stream using short overlapping frames. From each frame, a selected set of descriptors is extracted. The aim is not exhaustive feature extraction, but the selective tracking of perceptually salient dimensions within electroacoustic material. Frame-based analysis is inherently dependent on windowing operations, which introduce spectral leakage and edge discontinuities (Harris 1978). Such discontinuities do not necessarily correspond to perceptually meaningful change, since auditory organisation operates over temporally integrated spans (Bregman 1990). To mitigate these effects, optional smoothing and value constraints may be applied to feature streams prior to visual mapping. These controls remain user-adjustable and allow the attenuation of extreme fluctuations that might otherwise produce visually disruptive outliers. However, discontinuities introduced by frame segmentation cannot be entirely eliminated. The reconciliation between analytical granularity and perceptual continuity remains a structurally challenging aspect of the process.

Each frame produces a configuration of feature values. These values, individually or in combination, are mapped onto visual parameters (Figure 1) that define the position and variation of a graphical trace, namely a line or a polygon. Visual continuity emerges from the sequential relation of these mapped configurations. The trace therefore functions as a projection of evolving feature relations across time.

Figure 1. Computational realisation of visual tracing. The audio stream is analysed in overlapping frames, generating feature configurations that are mapped to graphical parameters. Visual continuity arises from the sequential relation of mapped frames, producing the final composite sketch.

A central perceptual distinction concerns the differentiation between pitch-dominated and noise-dominated material. This distinction is not imposed categorically but derived from

periodic stability, estimated through the voicing probability of the pYIN algorithm (Mauch and Dixon 2014). Higher periodic stability indicates tonal organisation, whereas lower values indicate noise-dominated or weakly periodic material.

In tonal passages, vertical position is derived from fundamental frequency (F0), estimated using the CREPE pitch estimator (Kim et al. 2018). When periodic stability decreases and a stable F0 cannot be reliably estimated, vertical position is derived from a loudness-weighted spectral centroid, allowing height to reflect the dominant distribution of spectral energy. Spectral centroid is widely associated with the perceptual dimension of timbral brightness and has been shown to interact with pitch perception or to function as a cue for pitch height in task-dependent contexts (Allen and Oxenham 2014; McPherson and McDermott 2018; Saitis and Siedenburg 2020). Periodicity further modulates visual scale: sounds with lower periodic stability generate visually expanded traces, whereas more stable tonal sounds produce comparatively compact forms. In this way, periodicity functions both as a differentiating mechanism and as a continuous modulator of visual scale.

Two rendering strategies implement these mappings. Line-based sketching maps feature values to the length, width, vertical position, colour saturation and lightness, angularity, and continuity of a line at each frame, producing a continuous trace over time. In polygon-based sketching (Figure 3), feature values determine the polygon's radius, number of vertices, vertical position, colour saturation and lightness, internal texture, and shape skewness. Successive forms reflect evolving configurations of features rather than discrete symbolic units.

Default mappings follow recurrent crossmodal tendencies (e.g., spectral height to vertical position, intensity to scale). However, these mappings remain adjustable and users may reconfigure feature-to-visual correspondences. The system therefore operates as a feature-tracing framework. It does not perform automatic object segmentation, nor does it claim to model perceptual grouping in full. Instead, it renders evolving configurations of selected features and, in some cases, their combinations, allowing perceptual structure to emerge through temporal continuity.

4. Controlled synthetic example

To examine the behaviour of the mapping strategies under controlled conditions, a synthetic example was constructed using simple waveforms and noise-based textures (Figure 2). The stimuli were intentionally designed to include opposing tonal glissandi, frequency-modulated sine tones and noise-based textures, enabling the behaviour of the visual mappings to be observed across both pitched and noise-dominated material. A simplified illustration of the basic mapping transformations was presented in our earlier SMC publication (Velenis et al. 2025). The present example extends that demonstration by using a controlled set of stimuli designed to expose the behaviour of combinational features, particularly the interaction between pitch-related and spectral descriptors in the visual rendering. The precise mathematical formulations of the combinational descriptors used in these mappings are presented in detail in Velenis et al. (2025). Here the focus lies on their perceptual consequences in the visual rendering.

All renderings share the same correspondences between auditory descriptors and visual parameters. Line width reflects sharpness, colour saturation corresponds to periodicity, colour

lightness represents loudness and angularity follows periodicity. The renderings differ only in the descriptors used to determine vertical position and line length.

In Mapping A, vertical position is derived from spectral centroid while line length corresponds directly to loudness. Because loudness affects all signals in a comparable manner, regardless of whether they are pitched or noise-dominated, both tonal and noise-based sounds produce similarly wide visual shapes. As a result, the visual scale does not differentiate between pitched and noisy material.

Mapping B partially mitigates this effect by scaling line length according to periodicity. Because tonal sounds typically exhibit higher periodicity values than noise textures, their visual shapes become more compact, producing a clearer distinction between pitched and noise-dominated material. However, the vertical ordering of pitched sounds remains incorrect because spectral centroid continues to determine vertical position for all sounds. As a result, pitched streams may visually intersect even when their pitch trajectories do not cross in the audio domain.

Mapping C assigns vertical position directly to fundamental frequency (F0), producing a correct relative ordering of pitched sounds. Nevertheless, noise-based sounds cannot be meaningfully positioned within this representation because they lack stable F0 estimates. As a result, noise-oriented segments collapse into visually ambiguous regions, limiting the representation of their internal spectral variation.

Finally, Mapping D introduces a combinational strategy. Vertical position is derived from F0 in pitch-dominated passages and from spectral centroid when periodic stability decreases. In this configuration, periodicity functions as a mediating descriptor that determines which spectral representation becomes visually dominant. Tonal sounds therefore retain coherent pitch trajectories, while noise-dominated material remains vertically differentiated through spectral centroid. This combinational approach produces a more balanced visual representation capable of accommodating both pitched and noisy material within the same framework. This example clarifies the behaviour of the mappings under simplified conditions. The following illustration (Figure 3) shows how the same framework operates when applied to real electroacoustic material.

Figure 2. Controlled synthetic example illustrating the behaviour of alternative feature-to-visual mapping strategies. Six audio streams generated through simple synthesis processes: (1) Sine-wave glissando A3–A4 followed by a descending harmonic sequence of seven semitones; later segments include glissandi A3–A4, A4–A5 and A4–A1. (2) Sawtooth glissando A3–A2 followed by an ascending harmonic sequence of nine semitones; later segments include glissandi A3–A2, A2–A1 and A1–A5. (3) Sine tone initially stable in frequency and gradually subjected to increasing LFO modulation, producing progressively denser frequency modulation. (4) Pink noise with fade-in and fade-out envelopes. (5) Sequential pink-noise segments filtered by band-pass filters centred at 942 Hz, 2.5 kHz and 6.2 kHz. (6) Continuous pink noise filtered by a moving band-pass filter whose centre frequency evolves from 260 Hz to higher spectral regions, reaching 11.1 kHz.

4.1 Musical illustration: Schaeffer excerpt (20–37 s)

To illustrate the behaviour of the system in electroacoustic material, a short excerpt from Pierre Schaeffer’s *Étude aux objets* (20–37 s) was analysed (Figure 3). The selected passage presents a sequence of relatively discrete sound events, including pitched beeps, descending glissandi, and noise-dominated impacts. Because the events occur in a largely monophonic stream, the excerpt provides a suitable context for observing how the visual mappings articulate individual sound objects over time.

The same feature mappings used in the controlled synthetic example are applied here, while only the rendering strategy differs. The comparison therefore focuses on the visual parameterisation of the descriptors rather than on the mapping strategy itself. In the line-based representation, the evolution of the descriptors appears as continuous trajectories across time. In this rendering mode, the visual representation is controlled through parameters such as line length, line width, angularity and line dashing, allowing variations in loudness, sharpness and periodicity to be expressed through changes in stroke geometry and continuity. In contrast, the polygon-based rendering translates the same descriptors into shape-oriented parameters, including radius, number of corners, skew and internal texture. This representation generates discrete geometric forms for each frame analysed whose size, skewness and surface texture reflect the underlying audio features.

Figure 3. Two visual renderings of an excerpt from Pierre Schaeffer’s *Étude aux objets* (20–37 s). Both renderings use the same underlying feature mappings but different visual parameterisations. The upper panel shows the line-based rendering, where audio descriptors control line length, line width, angularity and line dashing. The lower panel presents a polygon-based rendering, where the same descriptors are expressed through geometric parameters including radius, number of corners, skew and internal texture.

5. Discussion

Soundsketcher should not be understood as a finished or exhaustive framework of perceptual visualisation. Rather, it represents a research direction that attempts to align perceptual considerations with computational rendering. The system explores how selected spectral and temporal features can be organised visually in a way that reflects perceptual tendencies, while acknowledging that any such mapping remains partial and provisional.

First, the current implementation relies on frame-based analysis. While this approach enables fine-grained tracking of feature variation, it also introduces structural limitations. Perceptual organisation does not operate as a succession of discrete frames; listeners integrate information across longer temporal spans. Frame-wise feature estimation is also sensitive to local irregularities, producing outliers or boundary artefacts at transient onsets, offsets, or frame transitions. When mapped directly to visual parameters, such discontinuities may lead to abrupt geometric changes that do not correspond to stable perceptual events. Addressing these issues requires strategies that integrate information across longer temporal windows or operate on higher-level sound objects rather than isolated frames. However, increasing the temporal integration window introduces a trade-off: while it may reduce local instability, it can also smooth or obscure rapid spectral fluctuations and transient events that often play an important role in the articulation of electroacoustic textures. Ongoing work therefore explores object-oriented strategies based on the organisation of audio embeddings, seeking to move beyond strictly frame-wise processing (Velenis et al. 2025).

Second, the present mappings rely on a limited set of combinational feature formulations. Although combinations such as F0-centroid differentiation or periodicity-based scaling provide perceptually meaningful contrasts, they do not exhaust the possible relations between auditory and visual dimensions. Further work is required to test additional combinational strategies, alternative weighting schemes, and dynamic interactions among features. Such exploration may reveal more stable or intuitive correspondences across modalities.

Third, the system's visual behaviour remains dependent on selected mapping choices. While default configurations are informed by research on crossmodal correspondences, these associations are neither universal nor context-independent. Systematic experimentation with alternative mappings and feature hierarchies is therefore necessary to clarify which relations consistently support perceptual intelligibility.

Finally, a crucial next step concerns evaluation. The extent to which the generated sketches are perceived as intuitive, coherent, or analytically informative must be examined empirically. User studies, comparative evaluations, and task-based assessments may help determine whether the system successfully externalises perceptual structure or merely produces visually plausible abstractions. In this sense, Soundsketcher should be regarded as an exploratory framework. Its value lies less in offering definitive visual translations of sound than in opening a structured field of investigation into how perceptual organisation in electroacoustic music may be computationally articulated through alternative mapping strategies.

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7. References

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